

Pyrolytic Derangement of *Bis*-(N-Diethyl Carbamyl) Disulphide

M. S. CHANDE and M. D. KULKARNI

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Nagpur-440 001

Manuscript received 29 January 1980, revised 22 July 1980, accepted 29 October 1980

Pyrolytic decomposition of *bis*-(N-diethyl carbamyl) disulphide has been found to afford diethylammonium diethylthiocarbamate, 1,1,3-triethyl urea, ethylene and elemental sulphur. The mechanism of the thermal decomposition is discussed. The synthesis of disulphide and diethylammonium diethylthiocarbamate has been described.

TETRAETHYL and tetramethyl thiuram disulphides are well-known rubber vulcanization accelerators.

Thermal decomposition of these compounds has been studied by Sahasrabudhey and Radhakrishnan^{1a} and Koch^{1b}. Chande and Tanksale² studied the reaction in detail and suggested mechanism for the formation of various products. For example, in the case of tetraethyl thiuram disulphide(I), in addition to earlier reported products viz., carbon-disulphide, elemental sulphur, diethylammonium diethylthiocarbamate(II), tetraethylthiocarbamide(III) and tetraethylthiuram monosulphide (IV), the 1,1,3-triethyl thiocarbamide(V) and ethylene were isolated. Ethylene was found to have been eliminated by *cis*-elimination process which was also observed³ in the thermal decomposition of S-ethyl N-dialkyl/diaryl/alkyl-aryl dithiocarbamates.

where Et = Ethyl, R₁ = R₂ = alkyl/aryl.

Tetraethylthiuram monosulphide(IV) also afforded similar products. It was, therefore, thought

worthwhile to attempt pyrolysis of *bis*-(N-diethyl carbamyl) disulphide(VI) which is similar to I in structure.

The synthesis of diethylammonium diethylthiocarbamate(VII) required for the preparation of VI was attempted by passing carbon oxysulphide gas through diethylamine in dry benzene/ether in cold. The bulk of the expected VII could not be isolated as it readily oxidized in air to the corresponding disulphide VI. Small quantities of VII were, however, found deposited in the tube through which the gas was passed. Evaporation of solvent even under vacuum afforded only VI.

Pyrolytic derangement of the disulphide VI was carried out at 150-60° when a yellow oil distilled out, a part of which solidified on cooling. The solid, m.p. 78°, on tlc in benzene showed the presence of VI and another product which on warming with dilute aqueous alkali eliminated diethylamine and on oxidation with iodine afforded VI. Attempt to purify the other compound failed. From the properties and analysis it was identified as diethylammonium diethyl thiocarbamate (VII). TLC of the oil in benzene showed the presence of VI and VII and in addition 1,1,3-triethyl urea (VIII).

On increasing the temperature of the bath to 180°, a deep yellow liquid started distilling out.

TLC of the oil in benzene and chloroform indicated the presence of VI-VIII. The pot residues were found to contain VI-VIII and elemental sulphur.

Examination of the gaseous products revealed the presence of ethylene, diethylamine and hydrogensulphide (traces).

The formation of ethylene in the pyrolytic decomposition of VI is suggestive of a *cis*-elimination reaction involving ethyl group(s) on nitrogen. It also explains the source of two ethylenic hydrogens in diethylammonium diethyl thiocarbamate (VII). 1,1,3-Triethylurea(VIII) can arise by the condensation of diethylamine and ethyl isocyanate which is far too reactive to stay free. Following mechanism is suggested which explains the various products formed in the thermal decomposition of VI.

It can be concluded that the pattern of pyrolytic decomposition of *bis*-(diethyl carbamyl) disulphide (VI), although appears to be complex, is similar to the thermal decomposition of tetraethylthiuram disulphide, monosulphide³ and S-ethyl N-disubstituted dithiocarbamate⁴ in which case ethylene was formed by a *cis*-elimination reaction.

Experimental

Carbon oxysulphide gas, required for the preparation of diethylammonium diethyl thiocarbamate(VII), was prepared by the action of aqueous sulphuric acid on ammonium thiocyanate⁴.

Preparation of diethylammonium diethylthiocarbamate(VII) and bis-(N-diethyl carbamyl) disulphide (VI): A slow stream of carbon oxysulphide gas was passed through a benzene solution of diethylamine (10 ml in 20 ml of benzene) for 5 hrs. The resulting reaction mixture was concentrated when a semisolid was obtained which was triturated with

ethanol and filtered (0.3 g), m.p. 66°. On crystallization from ethanol or benzene, m.p. 68°; found N, 10.59; S, 24.41; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$ requires N, 10.60; S, 24.24%. It was hygroscopic and did not decompose on treatment with alkali. It was identified as *bis*-(diethyl carbamyl) disulphide(VI). Small quantities of colourless crystalline solid were always deposited in the tube through which gas was passed. It was removed by scrapping and washed with cold dry ether, m.p. 78°. It was soluble in water. On treatment with hot alkali, it decomposed liberating diethylamine and on oxidation with iodine gave VI. It was identified as diethylammonium diethylthiocarbamate(VII). Further identification of VI and VII was done by thin layer chromatography (*vide infra*).

Pyrolysis of bis-(N-diethyl carbamyl) disulphide (VI): *Bis*-(N-diethyl carbamyl) disulphide (8 g) was heated on an oil bath at 150-65° when a yellowish oil distilled out. The oil was collected by cooling the receiver in ice-bath when a part of it solidified into colourless needles. The distillate at this temperature strongly smelt of diethylamine. On increasing the temperature of the bath to 185°, a dark yellow oil distilled out which was collected separately.

The gases evolved during the pyrolysis were first passed through aqueous alkali solution (20%) and then through mercuric acetate solution (0.5 g in 70% acetic acid⁵).

The colourless crystalline solid, m.p. 78° (1.9 g) was thin layer chromatographed using silica gel (NCL grade) in benzene when it gave two spots on development with iodine vapours. The spot with $\text{Rf}=0.42$ was identified as the disulphide VI.

TLC of the solid in ethanol and chloroform also showed the presence of VI (Rf s 0.769 and 0.86 respectively) in it. The spot which did not run was due to diethyl ammonium diethylthiocarbamate (VII) which was identified by its ready decomposition into diethylamine on heating with aq. alkali and also by its oxidation to VI with iodine. Attempts to purify VII, however, failed probably because it readily oxidized in air to VI.

Examination of the oil: The yellow oil was taken up in acetone. TLC of the acetonetic solution in benzene showed the presence of three spots on development with iodine-vapours. The spot with $\text{Rf}=0.421$ was identified as due to VI by co-chromatography with an authentic sample prepared as described earlier (*vide supra*). The spot with $\text{Rf}=0.11$ was identified as due to triethyl urea(VIII) on comparison with an authentic sample prepared by the action of diethylamine on S-ethyl ethylthiocarbamate⁵. The spot which did not run was probably due to VII.

TLC of the oil in chloroform also showed the presence of three spots with Rf s=0.86 and 0.20, identified as due to VI and VIII respectively. The spot which did not run was probably due to VII. The products were separated by column chromatography using silica column (BDH grade) and

benzene as eluent. The first fractions contained VI. On further elution of the column, VIII was isolated (m.p. and m.m.p. 63° with authentic sample). The column was then eluted with methanol and from the methanolic eluate, VII was isolated by precipitation with dry ether, m.p., m.m.p. 78° with authentic sample.

Examination of the residue: The residue obtained on the pyrolytic decomposition of VI was taken up in acetone and filtered. The acetone insoluble part was found to be elemental sulphur identified through m.m.p. (113°). TLC of the acetonetic solution in benzene gave the same spots as were obtained in the tlc of the yellow oil in benzene (*vide supra*).

Examination of the mercuric acetate solution and aqueous alkaline solution in the traps: TLC of the mercuric acetate solution using propanol : triethylamine : water (50 : 25 : 25) gave a bluish white spot (Rf=0.71) due to ethylene on development with diphenyl carbazide. The authentic sample of ethylene was prepared by the action of zinc on ethylene dibromide^{2,3}.

Paper chromatography (ascending technique) of the mercuric acetate solution on Whatman no. 1 using the above solvent medium gave two spots with diphenyl carbazide. The blue spot with

Rf=0.73 was identified as due to ethylene and the spot which did not run was probably due to mercuric acetate.

The aqueous alkaline solution, on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid, liberated hydrogen sulphide probably formed by the interaction of carbon oxysulphide with alkali.

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to Prof. V.V. Deshpande, Head, Department of Chemistry and Dr. A. Gopalkrishna, Director, Institute of Science, Nagpur, for providing necessary facilities.

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